

Heritage building restoration and adaptive reuse- a challenge

Basudeb Malik

Keeper of Bhaskar Bhawan State Museum & OSD, West Bengal Heritage Commission

Email: basudebmalik@yahoo.com

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Abstract

Usually, a heritage building is more than hundred years old and was constructed for the purpose it required in the past. But in today's scenario its use may be different, as per the need of the time. When a building is selected for its reuse for a different purpose which was not the original one when it was constructed, it is called 'adaptive reuse of the building'. The challenge of restoration of a heritage building is not only adopting proper measures for conservation of the old building but also it is an important aspect for the restorer to have aprior knowledge about the after usage of the building. The concept of adaptive reuse of the heritage building is an important issue. This paper tries to highlight the adaptive re-use of Heritage building through some real -life cases.

Key words- Heritage, Adaptive reuse, Restoration

Introduction

The challenge of restoration of a heritage building is not only adopting proper measures for conservation of the old building but also it is an important aspect for the restorer to have aprior knowledge about the after usage of the building. In other words the person who is assigned for the restoration job of should have a clear idea about the building's fate. Restoration of heritage building should be designed as per the future use of the building. That is to decide, how the building

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would be utilized after its restoration. Would it be used as an institutional building, hotel, resort or for any other purpose! Sometimes a dilapidated heritage structure is restored spending large amount of fund but after the restoration the building is not brought to use in proper manner for some unknown reason. As a result within a few years once again it goes to the same dilapidated condition. A proper planning and coordination is required among the stakeholders of heritage.

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The built heritage may be categorized in to religious and secular types. Religious architectures comprised of temple, mosque, imambara, stupa, chaitya, gurduwara, church, convent, chapel, cemetery, synagogue etc and the secular structures comprised of palace, fort, educational Institutes, ancient tank, zamindar house, house of eminent persons, bridge, rail way station, wire house, industrial building etc.

In case of religious buildings usually the future use remains the same after restoration. Dilapidated mosque, temple or a church is used for the same purpose after the restoration. But the future use of the secular buildings is not always ascertained at the beginning of restoration as to what would be the exact purpose of the same. It should be decided well in advance before the start of restoration of the building, whereas, it has been found in some cases that there is no clear direction regarding the 'after use' of the building when the restoration started.

A Zamindar Bari may be enlisted as heritage for its architectural excellence. But it may become difficult for the present owner to maintain it in the changing socio- economic scenario. Nowadays nuclear families have replaced the Joint families. Zamindari is no more in practice, maintenance of palaces and mansions have become a tough task. It is also a ground reality that the present owner of a Zamindar Bari may not have the capacity to spend the required amount of money for the maintenance of the building which he inherited from his forefathers. Also, maintenance of heritage building is not at all an easy exercise. Expert mason and workers are to be found out who know the use of traditional building materials. That expertise of masonry is rare nowadays. The building materials have changed to a great extent. The lime-surki mortar is no more in use. Traditional roof made of lime-surki ramming with *kori-borga* beams are no more used. The old wooden doors and windows have become obsolete now. Under this situation the owner faces great difficulties to maintain the heritage building even if he has the financial capacity and desire for its preservation. The present owner of a grand building is somewhat compelled to explore the opportunities of earning from the building for sustenance. Further, with steep escalation of price of real estate the owner of the Zamindar Bari is often allured by the land sharks for construction of new building for commercial purpose demolishing the old one. In present socio-political situation there is real threat of losing our built heritage. Further, in current situation there is threat from the building promoters who often unethically pressurize and tempt the owner of a heritage building for constructions of flats and indulge in profit making business. For these so called promoter class the heritage value of a building is insignificant. Their only intention is to acquire land and construct building felling the old ones. This activity is causing harm towards our built heritage and the environment.

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Coming to the heritage enlistment and protection there are large numbers of secular and religious structures having heritage merits yet not enlisted by any of the authorities' viz. the Archaeological Survey, State Archaeology Departments or Kolkata Municipal Corporation. The criteria for inclusion as archaeological monuments are not fulfilled by those structures and as a result are not included. The West Bengal Heritage Commission, other than the archaeology departments is empowered for declaration of buildings as heritage if the structures fulfill the heritage criteria as prescribed in the West Bengal Heritage Commission Act 2001. Thus many of those left out structures come under the Commission's purview. As a major activity of the Commission the enlistment of heritage building is done as a continuous process. So far the Commission has enlisted about five hundred buildings in the state and many more are under immediate consideration. It may be mentioned here that the Coochehar and Nabadwip towns have been considered as places of heritage importance where about 155 and 102 properties were identified for heritage.

The concept of adaptive reuse of the heritage building is an important issue. With the passage of time the requirement and use of the heritage building may change. A heritage building may be used for a different purpose from its original use keeping the architectural features intact. The façade and other interesting architectural members of the building should be preserved as far as possible. There are many instances when the palaces or the Raj Baris had been converted into universities, colleges, schools, museums hotels, resorts etc keeping the old architectural features intact. In that case, for the adaptive reuse of the buildings, certain modification may be brought in. That is why the prior knowledge about the 'after use' of the heritage building is important for the restorer. Unless the restorer knows the future use of the building, it becomes difficult to do the job perfectly. For instance, if a huge palace is converted into a museum suddenly after the completion of the restoration it will be quite difficult to satisfy its purpose properly. The height of the rooms of the palace and the space available may not be suitable for housing a museum of a particular type. For display, illumination, sale counter, auditorium, security room etc of the museum the palace should be restored accordingly introducing some modification within permissible limit.

In our country the concept of restoration of heritage building is at a juvenile state. Our awareness on heritage has only started since recent past. There is no room for doubt to state that we are lacking expertise in this field. There are a very few qualified people who have sound knowledge on restoration of heritage building.

The major agencies in the state and in the centre are the PWD and CPWD who are given the responsibility for repair and restoration of the heritage buildings owned by the government. These agencies have very few resource persons to execute the job properly. It has been found that during the course of restoration the PWD and the CPWD often digress from the norms of heritage restoration unknowingly. There is lacuna of knowledge for the use of traditional material for restoration. The knowledge of how to restore with the similar materials which was originally used at the time of construction of the building is lacking. They have little exposure about the traditional method of processing of the mortar for restoration of building. Often it has been noticed that for the agencies, the restoration of a heritage building means repair, replication and ornamentation. And finally providing a glossy look to the old structure. Such type of work cannot be claimed as heritage restoration and is totally against the ethics of restoration as laid down in the UNESCO guidelines.

It is advisable to introduce 'heritage cell' in the government construction departments. There is ample

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scope for improvement in the concept of heritage restoration in our county.

The role of a qualified heritage restorer is very important for restoration of heritage buildings which maybe brought under adaptive reuse. For example if a jail building is adapted to house a museum then it becomes really a challenging task for a restorer to bring about necessary modifications while restoring the building. The jail architecture is different from museum architecture but since an old jail building is supposed to be restored as a museum it should be always kept in mind that maximum architectural features of the jail architecture should be kept as the built legacy. There may be a long history with the jail building as well. An ordinary building restorer may destroy certain features of the jail building which appear less significant to him. He may not consider them important because of its new use as museum. But a true heritage restorer will give importance to those features of the jail architecture. He should have the insight of preserving the old features of the buildings that connect the history of the area. Somebody may think why a museum should look like a jail. Usually a jail building is covered with high walls and the entry point may be through a small Iron Gate. Keeping the features of a jail and converting the interior of the building for display of a museum would be the real task of a qualified heritage conservator. Such actions reflect how far he is following the ethics of heritage restoration. If the old architecture of a jail is destroyed then the history of the building would be destroyed too.

A good attempt has been made to convert the Balurghat jail building as a cultural museum by the Govt. of West Bengal. The Danish Governor House at Serampore which is a current project is being reused as a govt office building and a museum. The Red Building which was the old land Registration Building in the Serampore Court Compound is being converted to a successful restaurant. The extremely dilapidated Denmark Tavern, at Serampore is a success story of restoration which became a grand restaurant and hotel. The Old Governor's House at Barrackpore after restoration has housed a beautiful museum. The Rabindrabhan at Manpoo the hill residence of Rabindranath Tagore, has been converted to a biographical museum on Rabindranath. These are some of the current restoration projects undertaken by the West Bengal Heritage Commission and the National Museum of Denmark jointly which may be cited as examples of adaptive reuse of heritage buildings in West Bengal.

Whether it is the same use or adaptive reuse preservation of the built heritage after restoration is a major responsibility which involves a thorough planning. There are two types of measures for preserving heritage building. 1) Preventive and 2) Curative. The curative measure is very complex and highly cost involving. However, the preventive measure is much simpler and very important for its preservation.

Following are a few tips for preventive restoration:

- 1) Cleaning debris and garbage from the roof and floor of the heritage structure regularly.
- 2) Removing vegetation regularly from the building and its adjoining area.
- 3) Anti termite treatment after every 1 to 2 years.
- 4) White washing with lime every three years and painting of wooden and iron components of the building time to time.
- 5) Cleaning of fungus by applying ammonium hydroxide solution on the outside walls of the building as and when required.

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- 6) Maintaining proper drainage for clearance of water.
- 7) Plinth protection to avoid any water logging in the building.
- 8) The building should not be kept under lock and key for long time. It should be used regularly and properly.
- 9) Natural light, air and proper ventilation should be allowed through the doors and windows.
- 10) Vandalism should be prevented by regular watch as far as possible.
- 11) If there is any sign of deterioration on the heritage structure immediate repair/ restoration should be done to stop major damage in future.

The Denmark Tavern, Serampore (before restoration)

The Denmark Tavern, Serampore (after restoration and brought to adaptive reuse in 2017-18)

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Red Building, Serampore (before restoration)

Red Building, Serampore (after restoration and put to adaptive reuse in 2019-20)

Danish Governor House, Serampore (before restoration)

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Danish Governor House, Serampore (after restoration and brought to adaptive use in 2020-21)

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Old Governor General's House, Barrackpore (before restoration)

Old Governor General's House, Barrackpore (after restoration and adaptive reuse in 2020-21)